

Aqueous Polymerization of Acrylamide Initiated by Hydrogen Peroxide-Hydroxylamine Redox Couple

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Conversion-time data were obtained for the polymerization of acrylamide in water initiated by hydrogen peroxide hydroxylamine redox pair. The polymerization was carried out under nitrogen at 30°; the yield was obtained gravimetrically, using an excess of methanol-acetone mixture as precipitant.

The effect of initiator concentration, monomer concentration and temperature have been studied. The overall activation energy between 30°-50° is about 6.5 Kcal/mole. It appears from the dependence of the rate of polymerization on the initiator concentration and endgroup analysis that a free radical mechanism is operative here.

POLYMERIZATION of acrylamide in aqueous solution has been carried out by a number of workers using γ -rays¹, x-rays², ultrasonic waves³, photoinitiator^{4,5} etc. Acrylamide also polymerises spontaneously, if the monomer is exposed to air for several weeks and then added to water at room temperature⁶. Redox polymerization of acrylamide include initiation by chlorate-sulfite⁷, persulfate-metabisulfite⁸, ceric(III)-3-chloro-1-propanol⁹, ferric-bisulfite¹⁰, persulfatethiosulfate^{11,12} and permanganate-oxalic acid¹³.

Dainton and co-workers¹⁴ have used hydrogen peroxide as a photoinitiator in this system. In order to study the effect of hydrogen peroxide as an oxidant, we have used H₂O₂-hydroxylamine hydrochloride redox couple and the results are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Water used as solvent, was prepared by distilling tap water with KMnO₄-NaOH mixture in an all-glass distilling apparatus. All experiments were carried out from the same stock of water to eliminate any error arising out of different quantity of metal ions present in differently treated types of water.

Acrylamide was recrystallised from chloroform. The recrystallised product was washed several times with benzene and then dried under vacuum at room temperature for 12-15 hr. The purified acrylamide was stored in nitrogen atmosphere over calcium chloride in the dark. Hydrogen peroxide and hydroxylamine hydrochloride used were of analytical grade and were not purified further.

Polymerization reactions were carried out in pyrex conical flasks of 150 ml volume fitted with air-tight glass stopper containing arrangement for nitrogen flushing and injection of catalyst etc. 25 ml was always the total liquid kept at 30°.

The system was deaerated by passing nitrogen for 10 min and then the conical flasks were kept in a constant temperature bath. Since, the polymers are soluble in water, non-solvent (methanol-acetone mixture) was added to precipitate the polymers at different intervals to stop the reaction. The rate of monomer disappearance was then measured gravimetrically by weighing the polymer formed.

The number of average molecular weight of the polymer was determined viscometrically in water at 30° from the intrinsic viscosity by $[\eta] = 6.8 \times 10^{-4} M^{-n^{0.66}}$.

Results and Discussion

The effect of hydrogen-peroxide: The effect of hydrogen peroxide at a fixed concentration of monomer, viz., 0.4 m/l and at a fixed concentration of NH₂OH.HCl viz., 1×10^{-2} m/l has been shown in Fig. 1. The rate dependence on [H₂O₂] is very interesting. In the concentration range 5×10^{-4} m/l to 1×10^{-2} m/l, the rate of polymerization was found to increase steadily with increasing the concentration of H₂O₂, then increases very slowly upto concentration 5×10^{-2} m/l above which the rate decreases steadily and rapidly. This is evidently due to the formation of oxygen from decomposition of hydrogen peroxide at a higher concentration. Thus H₂O₂ acts as a retarder above the concentration 5×10^{-2} m/l in this system.

The plot (Fig. 3) of rate of polymerization against square root of H₂O₂ concentration shows a linear graph upto concentration 1×10^{-2} m/l then rate decreases due to the retarding action of H₂O₂. Therefore, rate of polymerization shows half-order dependence on H₂O₂ concentration. Variation of molecular weight with H₂O₂ concentration has shown in Fig. 4; with increasing concentration of H₂O₂ molecular weight first increases slowly, then after

Fig. 1. Yield-time curve of acrylamide polymerization at 30° using 1×10^{-2} m/l $[\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}]$ 0.4M Monomer with varying $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$
 A 5×10^{-1} m/l; B 1×10^{-1} m/l; C 5×10^{-2} m/l;
 D 2.5×10^{-2} m/l; E 1×10^{-2} m/l; F 5×10^{-3} m/l;
 G 1×10^{-3} m/l; H 5×10^{-4} m/l.

Fig. 2. Yield-time curve at 30° at 1×10^{-2} m/l $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$ 0.4M Monomer and varying $[\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}]$
 A 1×10^{-1} m/l; B 5×10^{-2} m/l; C 1×10^{-2} m/l;
 D 5×10^{-3} m/l; E 1×10^{-3} m/l.

2.5×10^{-2} m/l H_2O_2 concentration it decreases. This also supports that at higher concentration H_2O_2 retards the reaction.

Fig. 3. R_p versus square root of Initiator concentration
 A $[NH_2OH.HCl]$ B $[H_2O_2]$.

The effect of hydroxylamine hydrochloride : The effect of hydroxylamine hydrochloride has been shown in Fig. 2. The concentration of hydroxylamine hydrochloride was varied from 1×10^{-3} to 1×10^{-1} m/l keeping the monomer concentration fixed at 0.4 m/l and that of H_2O_2 at 1×10^{-2} m/l. The rate of polymerization was found to increase with increasing concentration of hydroxylamine

hydrochloride. The plot (Fig. 3) of rate of polymerization versus square root of initiator concentration yields a linear graph showing the half-order dependence on hydroxylamine-hydrochloride concentration. The variation of molecular weight with hydroxylamine hydrochloride concentration also shows the normal behaviour, i.e., the molecular weight decreases with increase of hydroxylamine HCl concentration (vide Fig. 4).

Effect of Monomer : Dependence of R_p on the concentration of monomer from 0.2 M to 0.8 M was shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 (Table 1) keeping the initiator concentration fixed at 1×10^{-2} m/l. The results show 1.45 order dependence on monomer concentration. Suen⁷ found that although initial rate depends on the first power of monomer concentration the time conversion data are best fitted by $5/2$ power on the monomer concentration. The reason for different dependence on $[M]$ is more difficult to explain, but the exponent 1.35 found by Schulz *et al.*¹ may have arisen due to high conversion of polymerization. We also find the monomer exponent to be 1.45 which fully supports the Schulz's result.

Based on the rate dependence, it is expected that molecular weight should depend more on the monomer concentration than on initiator. The dependence of molecular weight on monomer concentration has been shown in Table 1. It appears from the results that the variation of molecular weight with variation of monomer concentration is much more pronounced than that of initiator concentrations (vide Fig. 4).

Effect of temperature : Rate of polymerization has been found to increase with increasing temperature (vide Table 2). Overall activation energy as calculated from the slope of the Arrhenius plot (Fig. 7) has been found to be 6.5 Kcal/mole within the temperature range $30^\circ-50^\circ$. The low activation energy of this system shows that this polymerization reac-

Fig. 4. log-log plot of molecular weight against initiator concentration :

- (A) represents $[NH_2OH.HCl]$ and
 (B) represents $[H_2O_2]$.

Fig. 5. Yield-time curve showing the monomer dependence on polymerization rate at 30° at $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] : 1 \times 10^{-2}$ m/l. $[\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}] : 1 \times 10^{-2}$ m/l and
 monomer A 0.8 m/l
 B 0.4 m/l
 C 0.2 m/l.

Fig. 6. log-log plot of the rate of polymerization against monomer concentration.

tion requires only little energy to propagate the reaction.

Probable Mechanism : It appears from the dependence of the rate of polymerization on initiator concentrations that a free-radical mechanism is

operative here. This is further supported by the fact that the conventional radical inhibitors *viz.*, hydroquinone, *p*-benzo-quinone etc. either inhibit or retard the reaction appreciably. The formation of a free radical in hydroxylamine-oxidant system may be visualized *via.*, the decomposition of hyponitrous

Fig. 7. Arrhenius plot for the determination of activation energy.

TABLE I

Yield-time Table $[H_2O_2] = 1 \times 10^{-2}$ m/l
 $[NH_2OH.HCl] = 1 \times 10^{-2}$ m/l

Conc. of monomer m/l	Polymerization time in minutes	% conversion	$\log \bar{M}_n$
0.2	20	14.5	4.301
	30	24.3	
	50	42.0	
	60	47.3	
0.4 M	20	19.5	4.571
	40	38.0	
	60	57.0	
	80	78.0	
0.8	7	8.88	4.761
	12	16.35	
	20	28.05	
	27	38.50	

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON R_p

Temperature	Polymerization time in minutes	Yield in %	$\log \bar{M}_n$
30°	20	19.5	4.571
	40	38.0	
	60	57.0	
	80	78.0	
40°	10	12.68	4.350
	15	19.93	
	30	40.10	
50°	10	18.06	4.175
	15	28.90	
	20	38.09	
	30	62.27	
	40	73.67	

acid which is a well-known intermediate in the oxidation reactions of hydroxylamine *viz.*,

Thus the scheme of initiation in the present case may be represented as

The direct verification of the presence of -OH group in aquo-soluble polyacrylamide is not possible through dye-technique¹⁵. However, its invariable presence as the initiating species in almost all cases of redox systems containing H_2O_2 as oxidant is demonstrated in earlier research works on aqueous polymerization¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

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